

Caring for Democracy: Life-Making Practices in Geopolitical Uncertainties

Version 1

Description

Amidst the looming war fears in Europe and emptying villages in border regions, whilst economic and political powers are concentrating in centers, the fate of democracy and a sense of normality lie not only in the strength of state institutions but, crucially, in the hands of decentralized communities that make up the fabric of a society at large. The key to resilience of a country against various disasters and chaos is the invisible force of life-making practices. From volunteer work in a local clean-up (talka) and help in finding a lost child, to support of lonely seniors, maintaining rituals, weddings and cemetery festivals, life-making encompass and intertwine various goals, but, taken together, they make life meaningful and livable. As the chain is as strong as its weakest link, the project draws its attention to Latgale in Latvia, the final frontier of Europe, bordering with Russia and Belarus, experiencing an information war waged by Kremlin forces, activities by antagonistic groups, economic deprivation and depopulation. Research into the communities and networks that make everyday life in Latgale is intermittent. It is imperative to study life-making 'bottom up' through the standpoints of those, who live in this border region. Geopolitical worries make this need urgent. Therefore, the aim of the project is to examine practices that sustain life in Latgale, focusing on seemingly disparate, resourceful communities and groups: hunters, mothers and youth activists.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Fundamental and Applied
Research

Researchers

Ieva Puzo (orcid:0000-0003-3197-0942), Aija Lulle (orcid:0000-0002-5386-9493), Valdis Krebs (0009-0000-8670-6175), Diana Kiscenko (orcid:0000-0003-0612-2001), Karlīna Grīviņa, Aiga Ļaksa, Elza Lāma (0000-0002-9271-3862), Anna Žabicka (0000-0003-0051-7379)

Organizations

Rīga Stradiņš University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Caring for Democracy: Life-Making Practices in Geopolitical Uncertainties](#)

Description:

Amidst the looming war fears in Europe and emptying villages in border regions, whilst economic and political powers are concentrating in centers, the fate of democracy and a sense of normality lie not only in the strength of state institutions but, crucially, in the hands of decentralized communities that make up the fabric of a society at large. The key to resilience of a country against various disasters and chaos is the invisible force of life-making practices. From volunteer work in a local clean-up (talka) and help in finding a lost child, to support of lonely seniors, maintaining rituals, weddings and cemetery festivals, life-making encompass and intertwine various goals, but, taken together, they make life meaningful and livable. As the chain is as strong as its weakest link, the project draws its attention to Latgale in Latvia, the final frontier of Europe, bordering with Russia and Belarus, experiencing an information war waged by Kremlin forces, activities by antagonistic groups, economic deprivation and depopulation. Research into the communities and networks that make everyday life in Latgale is intermittent. It is imperative to study life-making 'bottom up' through the standpoints of those, who live in this border region. Geopolitical worries make this need urgent. Therefore, the aim of the project is to examine practices that sustain life in Latgale, focusing on seemingly disparate, resourceful communities and groups: hunters, mothers and youth activists.

Researchers:

[Ieva Puzo \(orcid:0000-0003-3197-0942\)](#)

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Organizations:

[Riga Stradiņš University](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [Fundamental and Applied Research](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Interview data

Semi-structured and unstructured interviews with research participants. At least 30 semi-structured in-depth interviews will be carried out among representatives of the main target groups: hunters, mothers, and youth activists.

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Purpose of the data collection/generation

The purpose of the data collection is to investigate the ecology of life-making practices in Latgale within the networks of hunters, mothers, and young activists.

The study will examine community ties and networks, everyday practices that

contribute to the well-being of families and individuals, and the often invisible work that supports community life and democratic processes.

Relation to the objectives of the project

The collected data will help achieve the project's two main objectives: first, to understand how life-making practices function within different community networks in Latgale, and second, to identify positive examples of resilient behaviour in the region. These insights will be used to develop a practical roadmap or "survival kit" for navigating polycrisis situations.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

- 1) Social science researchers at RSU, other national and international research institutions
- 2) Policy makers, municipalities
- 3) NGOs
- 4) Other stakeholders

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

3-6 GB (including audio recordings and their transcriptions)

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

The project does not plan to use existing or reusable datasets. Currently, there are no available datasets that capture the specific community networks, life-making practices, and everyday forms of support examined in this study, particularly within the context of hunters, mothers, and young activists in Latgale. Therefore, the research requires the generation of original qualitative data through interviews in order to address the objectives of the project.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

Questionnaire

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

PDF is an open data format.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Standard office software can be used to open and access PDF files.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

CC BY is one of the most open licences that endorses re-use.

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

No

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2029-01-01

RSU Dataverse stores research data unlimited time period

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security
- Processing
- Long-term preservation

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

RSU ensures the IT infrastructure for storage, archiving, re-use, security, long-term preservation free of charge. Data processing has to be covered by project grant and carried out by project personnel.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data? Which institution(s) are the data controller in this project?

Riga Stradiņš University

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project? Which person will be the data manager responsible for the correct processing of data in the project, staff training, and maintenance of the data management plan?

- Diana Kiscenko (orcid: [0000-0003-0612-2001](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0612-2001))
- Ieva Puzo (orcid: [0000-0003-3197-0942](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3197-0942))

Diāna Kiščenko:

1) will be responsible for preparing the Data Management Plan and updating it during the project if necessary;

2) will also prepare the data storage space on the RSU SharePoint;

3) guide colleagues on proper data processing and storage;

4) and ensure that data are deleted in accordance with the timelines specified in the Data Management Plan.

Ieva Puzo, as the project leader, will oversee the overall process and ensure that the data management procedures are followed as planned.

3.1.5 Who will collect and process the data for this study (name data processors-researchers, laboratory technicians, assistants, and other persons who will work with the data for this study)?

- Ieva Puzo (orcid: [0000-0003-3197-0942](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3197-0942))
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- Karlīna Grīviņa
- Anna Žabicka (0000-0003-0051-7379)
- Elza Lāma (0000-0002-9271-3862)
- Aiga Ļaksa

Comment:

Each researcher will be responsible for the following tasks: data collection, data cleaning, data analysis, structuring and organizing the data, validation, and other related research activities.

3.1.6 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Yes, several data quality assurance processes are foreseen. Semi-structured interviews will be conducted using a common interview guide to ensure consistency across interviews. All interviews will be audio-recorded and

transcribed, and the transcripts will be checked against the recordings to ensure accuracy. The data will also be carefully organised, anonymised where necessary, and securely stored to maintain the reliability and integrity of the dataset.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

RSU IT infrastructure ensures the security measures listed above, RSU Sharepoint is used for data storage

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

RSU IT infrastructure ensures the security provisions listed above, RSU Sharepoint is used for data storage.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research? For how long the data will be stored there?

1. Raw data (audio files with full-length interviews) will be stored in the RSU SharePoint till the interview transcript is prepared. There are several ways how the data could be obtained and stored.

1.1. In-person interviews will be recorded using a voice recorder.

We'll record the audio file using VoiceRecorder and, as soon as possible, store it in the RSU SharePoint in a specially designed location.

1.2. In-person interviews will be transcribed by hand. Those transcribed by hand will be stored at the Faculty of Social Science, Kuldīgas 9c, Riga, Latvia, in a specially designed, locked safe.

1.3. Remote interviews will be recorded using Microsoft Teams, and the recordings will be automatically saved to Microsoft SharePoint. Before the recording begins, the interviewee will be informed that it will be recorded. The audio recording (without direct identifiers) will be stored in a secure RSU-provided cloud storage.

2. Pseudonymized data (interview transcript) will be stored in the RSU SharePoint for the duration of the research period and for two years after the research period ends, to support the preparation of scientific articles.

3. The pseudonymization key will be stored in Nextcloud and deleted at the end of the research period (i.e., at the end of the project).

3.2.4 When and how will data from the specified storage location be deleted or destroyed?

- Data is stored electronically, the deletion process will be carried out as per instructions by RSU IT services.
- Physical paper documents (if interviews will be written down by hand) will be destroyed mechanically (shredding). Shredding will be done as per RSU regulations and proven by signed destruction act.

3.2.5 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

RSU Dataverse has all the necessary measures to ensure secure long-term preservation and curation.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The interview data, even pseudonymized, may reveal personal details and the identity of research participants. Complete anonymization for interview data may not be possible.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is it planned to conduct an informed consent process for research subjects?

Yes

3.3.4 Where and for how long will the signed informed consent forms be stored? Who will have access to these documents?

The signed informed consent forms will be stored at the Faculty of Social Sciences of Rīga Stradiņš University (Kuldīgas iela 9C, Riga, Latvia). The documents will be kept in a specially designated locked safe to ensure secure storage. Access to the consent forms will be restricted and granted only to officially employed members of the research team involved in the project. The forms will be stored during the project and 3 years after the end of the project. Signed informed consent forms will be destroyed as per RSU regulations and proven by signed destruction act.

3.3.5 Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.6 Will data collected/generated include personal data or any other sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.7 Is the collected/generated data intended to be processed outside the EU?

No

3.3.8 Is the collected/generated personal data intended to be used for profiling and/or automated decision-making?

No

3.3.9 Is artificial intelligence intended to be used in the processing of collected/generated sensitive or personal data?

No

3.3.10 What methods do you intend to use to process and access the data securely?

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Social network survey data

The social network survey will examine how families in Latgale connect with one another and with others in the community. The research will assess the extent of family integration and identify the local and transnational places, events, and memberships that bring people together and support the formation of informal networks. The analysis of ties will focus on both bonding and bridging social capital in Latgale. No family or individual names, or any other personal or identifying information, will be collected or used in the survey or subsequent analysis. The survey data will be integrated with approximately 30 semi-structured and unstructured interviews conducted with research participants, including hunters, mothers, and youth activists.

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection is to investigate how families in Latgale form and sustain social connections within local communities and across transnational contexts, in line with the project's objective to understand the social dynamics and life-making practices shaping the region. The study specifically aims to assess the extent of family integration and to identify the places, events, and memberships that facilitate the development of informal networks, with a focus on bonding and bridging social capital.

The data will originate exclusively from a social network survey conducted within the framework of semi-structured and unstructured interviews with research participants, including hunters, mothers, and youth activists.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

- 1) Social science researchers at RSU, other national and international research institutions
- 2) Policy makers, municipalities
- 3) NGOs
- 4) Other stakeholders

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

2-5 MB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

The project does not plan to use existing or reusable datasets. Currently, there are no available datasets that capture the specific community networks, particularly within the context of hunters, mothers, and young activists in Latgale. Therefore, the research requires the generation of original qualitative data through a social network survey in order to address the objectives of the project.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

Questionnaire

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

PDF is an open data format.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Standard office software can be used to open and access PDF files.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

CC BY is one of the most open licences that endorses re-use.

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

No

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2029-01-01

RSU Dataverse stores research data unlimited time period.

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage

- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security
- Processing
- Long-term preservation

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

RSU ensures the IT infrastructure for storage, archiving, re-use, security, long-term preservation free of charge. Data processing has to be covered by project grant and carried out by project personnel.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data? Which institution(s) are the data controller in this project?

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Comment:

Each researcher will be responsible for the following tasks: data collection, data cleaning, data analysis, structuring and organizing the data, validation, and other related research activities.

3.1.6 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Yes, several data quality assurance processes are foreseen. A social network survey will be done using a common survey form to ensure consistency across data collection. The data will also be carefully organised, anonymised where necessary, and securely stored to maintain the reliability and integrity of the dataset.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall

- Passwords

RSU IT infrastructure ensures the security measures listed above, RSU Sharepoint is used for data storage.

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

RSU IT infrastructure ensures the security provisions listed above, RSU Sharepoint is used for data storage.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research? For how long the data will be stored there?

Raw data (survey forms) will be stored in the RSU SharePoint for the duration of the research period and for two years after the research period ends, to support the preparation of scientific articles. No family or individual names, or any other personal or identifying information, will be collected or used in the survey or subsequent analysis.

3.2.4 When and how will data from the specified storage location be deleted or destroyed?

- Data is stored electronically, the deletion process will be carried out as per instructions by RSU IT services.
- Physical paper documents will be destroyed mechanically (shredding). Shredding will be done as per RSU regulations and proven by signed destruction act.

3.2.5 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

RSU Dataverse has all the necessary measures to ensure secure long-term preservation and curation.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

No family or individual names, or any other personal or identifying information, will be collected or used in the survey or subsequent analysis.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is it planned to conduct an informed consent process for research subjects?

Yes

3.3.4 Where and for how long will the signed informed consent forms be stored? Who will have access to these documents?

Informed consent may be obtained in two formats.

1. First, it may be provided digitally, either by signing with a secure e-signature or by signing a printed form and submitting a scanned copy. In such cases, the informed consent forms will be stored securely in the RSU SharePoint.

2. Second, informed consent may be obtained in a physical format, with participants signing the form by hand on paper. The signed informed consent

forms will be stored at the Faculty of Social Sciences of Rīga Stradiņš University (Kuldīgas iela 9C, Rīga, Latvija). The documents will be kept in a specially designated locked safe to ensure secure storage.

Access to the consent forms will be restricted and granted only to officially employed members of the research team involved in the project.

The forms will be stored during the project and 3 years after the end of the project. Signed informed consent forms will be destroyed as per RSU regulations and proven by signed destruction act.

3.3.5 Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.6 Will data collected/generated include personal data or any other sensitive information?

No

3.3.10 What methods do you intend to use to process and access the data securely?

Data accompanied by informed consent statements

Survey data

A country-wide survey, representative of Latvian society and with a focus on Latgale, exploring the awareness and participation in various life-making practices in support of the local community, as there is currently no such data in Latvia.

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Purpose of the data collection/generation

The purpose of the data collection is to investigate the ecology of life-making practices in Latgale within the networks of hunters, mothers, and young activists. The study will examine community ties and networks, everyday practices that contribute to the well-being of families and individuals, and the often invisible work that supports community life and democratic processes.

Relation to the objectives of the project

The collected data will help achieve the project's two main objectives: first, to understand how life-making practices function within different community networks in Latgale, and second, to identify positive examples of resilient behaviour in the region. These insights will be used to develop a practical roadmap or "survival kit" for navigating polycrisis situations.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

The data might be useful to:

- 1) Social science researchers at RSU, other national and international research institutions
- 2) Policy makers, municipalities
- 3) NGOs
- 4) Other stakeholders

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- CSV
- XLS

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

5-20 MB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

The project does not plan to use existing or reusable datasets. Currently, there are no available datasets that capture the specific community networks, life-making practices, and everyday forms of support examined in this study, particularly within the context of hunters, mothers, and young activists in Latgale. Therefore, the research requires the generation of original qualitative data through interviews in order to address the objectives of the project.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

- Codebook
- Questionnaire

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

PDF and CSV are an open data formats.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Standard office software can be used to open and access PDF, CSV files.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

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2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

No

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2029-01-01

RSU Dataverse stores research data unlimited time period.

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security
- Processing
- Long-term preservation

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

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Ieva Puzo, as the project leader, will oversee the overall process and ensure that the data management procedures are followed as planned.

3.1.5 Who will collect and process the data for this study (name data processors- researchers, laboratory technicians, assistants, and other persons who will work with the data for this study)?

Elza Lāma (0000-0002-9271-3862)

Comment:

The researcher will be responsible for organising the survey process (data collection, data cleaning, data analysis, structuring and organising the data, validation, and other related research actions).

3.1.6 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Yes, data quality assurance processes are foreseen. During data collection, built-in validation checks (e.g., mandatory fields, skip logic) will be used. After collection, data will be cleaned and validated (e.g., checking for missing values, inconsistencies, and duplicates), and all processing steps will be documented.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

RSU IT infrastructure ensures the security measures listed above, RSU Sharepoint is used for data storage

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

- Data sharing

RSU IT infrastructure ensures the security provisions listed above, RSU Sharepoint is used for data storage.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research? For how long the data will be stored there?

The survey will be conducted digitally (the specific tool has not yet been determined).

Raw survey data will be stored securely on the RSU server during the research. Processed data will be stored for the duration of the project and up to 2 years after completion. Access will be restricted to authorized research team members.

3.2.4 When and how will data from the specified storage location be deleted or destroyed?

- Data is stored electronically, the deletion process will be carried out as per instructions by RSU IT services.

3.2.5 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

RSU Dataverse has all the necessary measures to ensure secure long-term preservation and curation.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The survey will be not collect direct identifiers, however risk of re-identification exist.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is it planned to conduct an informed consent process for research subjects?

Yes

3.3.4 Where and for how long will the signed informed consent forms be stored? Who will have access to these documents?

In the case of an electronic survey, informed consent will be obtained digitally prior to participation (e.g., via a consent checkbox). No separate signed consent forms will be collected.

Consent records will be stored together with the survey data in a secure RSU storage system (e.g., SharePoint) for the duration of the project and up to 3 years after its completion.

Access will be restricted to authorised members of the research team.

3.3.5 Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.6 Will data collected/generated include personal data or any other sensitive information?

No

3.3.10 What methods do you intend to use to process and access the data securely?

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Field notes

The field notes are generated within the ethnographic component of the LALIFE project, which applies qualitative research methods to understand life-making practices and social networks among families and communities in Latgale. The purpose of the field notes is to document observations from participant observation, involving prolonged engagement and participation in the everyday lives of research participants, including hunters, mothers, and youth activists.

These data provide contextual, processual, and relational insights that complement interviews and survey data, supporting the project's objective to analyse how social ties, practices, and informal networks are formed and maintained, as well as how bonding and bridging social capital operate in the region.

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Purpose of the data collection/generation

The purpose of the data collection is to investigate the ecology of life-making practices in Latgale within the networks of hunters, mothers, and young activists. The study will examine community ties and networks, everyday practices that contribute to the well-being of families and individuals, and the often invisible work that supports community life and democratic processes.

Relation to the objectives of the project

The collected data will help achieve the project's two main objectives: first, to understand how life-making practices function within different community networks in Latgale, and second, to identify positive examples of resilient behaviour in the region. These insights will be used to develop a practical roadmap or "survival kit" for navigating polycrisis situations.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

- 1) Social science researchers at RSU, other national and international research institutions
- 2) Policy makers, municipalities
- 3) NGOs
- 4) Other stakeholders

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

20-50 MB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

The project does not plan to use existing or reusable datasets. Currently, there are no available datasets that capture the specific community networks, life-making practices, and everyday forms of support examined in this study, particularly within the context of hunters, mothers, and young activists in Latgale. Therefore, the research requires the generation of original qualitative data through participant observations in order to address the objectives of the project.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

Methodology description

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

PDF is an open data format.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Standard office software can be used to open and access PDF files.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

CC BY is one of the most open licences that endorses re-use.

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Due to the highly sensitive and context-rich nature of ethnographic field notes collected through participant observation, the data may contain indirect identifiers and detailed descriptions that could make participants recognizable, even after anonymization. As such, it is not possible to fully de-identify these data without significantly compromising their analytical value.

To protect participants' privacy and confidentiality, access to the field notes will be limited to the research team only and will not be made publicly available. This restriction is in line with ethical research standards and the informed consent provided by participants.

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

Yes

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2029-01-01

RSU Dataverse stores research data unlimited time period

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security
- Processing
- Long-term preservation

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

RSU ensures the IT infrastructure for storage, archiving, re-use, security, long-term preservation free of charge. Data processing has to be covered by project grant and carried out by project personnel.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data? Which institution(s) are the data controller in this project?

Riga Stradiņš University

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project? Which person will be the data manager responsible for the correct processing of data in the project, staff training, and maintenance of the data management plan?

- Diana Kiscenko (orcid: [0000-0003-0612-2001](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0612-2001))
- Ieva Puzo (orcid: [0000-0003-3197-0942](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3197-0942))

Diāna Kiščenko:

1) will be responsible for preparing the Data Management Plan and updating it during the project if necessary;

2) will also prepare the data storage space on the RSU SharePoint;

3) guide colleagues on proper data processing and storage;

4) and ensure that data are deleted in accordance with the timelines specified in the Data Management Plan.

Ieva Puzo, as the project leader, will oversee the overall process and ensure that the data management procedures are followed as planned.

3.1.5 Who will collect and process the data for this study (name data processors-researchers, laboratory technicians, assistants, and other persons who will work with the data for this study)?

- Ieva Puzo (orcid: [0000-0003-3197-0942](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3197-0942))
- Valdis Krebs (0009-0000-8670-6175)
- Diana Kiscenko (orcid: [0000-0003-0612-2001](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0612-2001))
- Aija Lulle (orcid: [0000-0002-5386-9493](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5386-9493))
- Karlīna Grīviņa
- Anna Žabicka (0000-0003-0051-7379)
- Elza Lāma (0000-0002-9271-3862)
- Aiga Ļaksa

Comment:

Each researcher will be responsible for the following tasks: data collection, data cleaning, data analysis, structuring and organizing the data, validation, and other related research activities.

3.1.6 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Yes, several data quality assurance processes are foreseen. Participant observations will be conducted using a common methodology to ensure consistency. Observations will be written down either on paper or digitally. The data will also be carefully organised, anonymised where necessary, and securely stored to maintain the reliability and integrity of the dataset.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

RSU IT infrastructure ensures the security measures listed above, RSU Sharepoint is used for data storage

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

RSU IT infrastructure ensures the security provisions listed above, RSU Sharepoint is used for data storage.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research? For how long the data will be stored there?

Raw data (field notes) will be stored in two formats:

1. Digital field notes will be stored in RSU SharePoint, in a private folder accessible only to the respective researcher.
2. Paper-based field notes, recorded in notebooks during fieldwork, will be stored securely in a locked cabinet at the host institution (RSU), with access restricted to authorised research team members only.

Raw data will be stored in the RSU SharePoint for the duration of the research period and for two years after the research period ends, to support the preparation of scientific articles.

3.2.4 When and how will data from the specified storage location be deleted or destroyed?

- Data is stored electronically, the deletion process will be carried out as per instructions by RSU IT services.

3.2.5 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

RSU Dataverse has all the necessary measures to ensure secure long-term preservation and curation.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The field notes, even pseudonymized, may reveal personal details and the identity of research participants. Complete anonymization for data may not be possible.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is it planned to conduct an informed consent process for research subjects?

No

3.3.6 Will data collected/generated include personal data or any other sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.7 Is the collected/generated data intended to be processed outside the EU?

No

3.3.8 Is the collected/generated personal data intended to be used for profiling and/or automated decision-making?

No

3.3.9 Is artificial intelligence intended to be used in the processing of collected/generated sensitive or personal data?

No

3.3.10 What methods do you intend to use to process and access the data securely?

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Policy document

Policy documents will be used in this project as a source of secondary data to analyse how life-making practices, community resilience, and regional development in Latgale are framed and governed at institutional and policy levels. These documents may include national, regional, and local policy strategies, development plans, and other relevant institutional texts.

The purpose of analysing policy documents is to contextualise empirical findings and to examine how state and institutional actors conceptualise and respond to issues such as depopulation, security, social cohesion, and everyday life in border regions. This analysis will complement qualitative data (e.g., interviews and participant observation) by providing insight into the normative and regulatory frameworks shaping local realities.

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Policy documents will be collected to analyse how life-making practices and community resilience in Latgale are framed and governed at policy and institutional levels, in line with the project's objectives. The data will originate from publicly available national, regional, and EU policy documents and will provide contextual and normative insights complementing qualitative research data.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

- 1) Social science researchers at RSU, other national and international research institutions
- 2) Policy makers, municipalities
- 3) NGOs
- 4) Other stakeholders

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

- Textual data
- Coded textual data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

50–250 MB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

The project does not plan to use existing or reusable datasets. Currently, there are no available datasets that capture the specific community networks, life-making practices, and everyday forms of support examined in this study, particularly within the context of hunters, mothers, and young activists in Latgale. Therefore, the research requires the generation of original qualitative data in order to address the objectives of the project.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

Methodology description

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

PDF is an open data format.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Standard office software can be used to open and access PDF files.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.1 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

RSU Dataverse

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

CC BY is one of the most open licences that endorses re-use.

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

No

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2029-01-01

RSU Dataverse stores research data unlimited time period

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security
- Processing
- Long-term preservation

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

RSU ensures the IT infrastructure for storage, archiving, re-use, security, long-term preservation free of charge. Data processing has to be covered by project grant and carried out by project personnel.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data? Which institution(s) are the data controller in this project?

Riga Stradiņš University

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Diāna Kiščenko:

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- Aija Lulle (orcid: [0000-0002-5386-9493](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5386-9493))
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- Elza Lāma (0000-0002-9271-3862)
- Aiga Ļaksa

Comment:

Each researcher will be responsible for the following tasks: data collection, data cleaning, data analysis, structuring and organizing the data, validation, and other related research activities.

3.1.6 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Yes, several data quality assurance processes are foreseen. Policy documents will be selected based on predefined inclusion criteria (e.g., relevance to the research topic, geographic scope, and institutional level) to ensure consistency and analytical coherence. Only official and publicly available documents from reliable sources (e.g., government institutions, regional authorities, and EU bodies) will be included.

All documents will be systematically organised and catalogued, including metadata such as source, publication date, and document type. Where necessary, documents will be checked for completeness and authenticity. The dataset will be stored in a structured format to support transparent and reproducible analysis.

These procedures will ensure the reliability, consistency, and traceability of the data used in the project.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

RSU IT infrastructure ensures the security measures listed above, RSU Sharepoint is used for data storage

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

RSU IT infrastructure ensures the security provisions listed above, RSU Sharepoint is used for data storage.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research? For how long the data will be stored there?

Policy documents will be stored in the RSU SharePoint in a designated project folder with controlled access for the research team. As these documents are publicly available and non-sensitive, no additional secure storage (e.g., locked safes or pseudonymisation procedures) is required.

All collected documents will be organised in a structured folder system, including metadata (e.g., source, date, document type) to support systematic analysis. Processed data (e.g., coded documents, analytical notes, or extracted excerpts) will also be stored in the same secure institutional environment.

The data will be stored for the duration of the research project and for at least two years after the end of the project to support the preparation of scientific publications and verification of results. Long-term preservation of relevant materials may be ensured through institutional repositories where appropriate.

3.2.4 When and how will data from the specified storage location be deleted or destroyed?

As the dataset consists of publicly available policy documents, the original documents do not require mandatory deletion. However, locally stored copies and derived data (e.g., annotated documents, coding files, analytical notes) will be managed according to institutional data management practices.

3.2.5 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

RSU Dataverse has all the necessary measures to ensure secure long-term preservation and curation.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.3 Is it planned to conduct an informed consent process for research subjects?

No

3.3.6 Will data collected/generated include personal data or any other sensitive information?

No

3.3.10 What methods do you intend to use to process and access the data securely?

National laws

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